

COMPARATIVE DAMAGE ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS OPEN CROSS-SECTION GLARE COMPOSITE COLUMNS

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SUBJECT OF CONSIDERATION

The subject of this research is a thin-walled column made of glass reinforced aluminium laminate (GLARE). Comprehensive numerical and experimental study was performed for different open cross-section columns that included top-hat-shaped sections. For each 7-layered GLARE column, the 3/2 laminate lay-ups were considered. Different stacking sequences were distinguished based on fibers alignment in the composite layer. Experimental failure test was performed in laboratory by a universal electromechanical strength-testing machine of Instron (maximum capacity 200 kN) upgraded with Zwick/Roel control software. Applied screw type testing machine provided a displacement control loading of 1 mm/min.

Aluminum 2024-T3		Composite TVR 380 M12/26%/R-glass	
E	72 GPa	$E_{1(1)}$	53.90 GPa
ν	0.33	$E_{T(2)}$	14.92 GPa
G	27.07 GPa	$E_{(3)}$	14.92 GPa
		G_{12}	5.49 GPa
		G_{23}	5.33 GPa
$R_{0.2}$	359 MPa	G_{13}	5.49 GPa
E_{tang}	720 MPa	ν_{12}	0.269
		ν_{23}	0.400
		ν_{23}	0.269

Sequence	Lay-up
1	Al/0/90/Al/90/0/Al
2	Al/90/0/Al/0/90/Al
3	Al/45/0/Al/0/45/Al
4	Al/0/45/Al/0/45/Al
5	Al/0/0/Al/0/0/Al
6	Al/25/0/Al/0/25/Al
7	Al/0/25/Al/25/0/Al

LINEAR BUCKLING ANALYSIS

Linear buckling analysis was performed to predict the lowest buckling modes for top-hat-shaped GLARE columns. Depending on the lay-up sequence, 4 or 5 half-waves appeared along the length of the column. FEM results were compared with experimental tests by DIC ARAMIS system.

Sample	FEM	ARAMIS DIC
O1 Al/0/90/Al/90/0/Al		
O3 Al/45/0/Al/0/45/Al		

ALUMINUM FAILURE PREDICTION

Huber-Mises-Hencky (H-M-H) criterion was used to calculate maps of equivalent stresses (EQVS) distribution. This enabled predicting failure initiation at the region, where EQVS exceeds material yield limit.

EQVS by Huber-Mises-Hencky criterion			Experiment
L1	L4	L7	

FAILURE CRITERIA AND PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS

Numerical failure simulation of fibre-reinforced composite layers included Tsai-Wu (TWSR), Hashin (HMAT, HFIB) and Puck (PMAT, PFIB) failure criteria application. By means of these criteria, failure factors (FF) were calculated and mapped onto the profile geometry in order to indicate particular regions greatly exposed to failure.

Study of thin-walled GLARE columns included also the progressive failure analysis (PFA). For that purpose, the Hashin criterion was applied to predict the onset of material damage. The damage evolution law after failure initiation was performed by the material property degradation method (MPDG).

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HFIB	HMAT	TWSR	
PFIB	PMAT	PFA - MPDG	EXPERIMENT